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IMPACT OF AI-POWERED LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS ON STUDENT PERFORMANCE AND TEACHER WORKLOAD AT THE NATIONAL OPEN UNIVERSITY NIGERIA

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Abstract: *This study investigates the impact of AI-powered learning management systems (LMS) on students' academic performance and teachers' workload at the National Open University Nigeria (NOUN), Ilorin study center. The purpose of this research is to find out the impact of AI powered learning management system on students' performance and investigate the impact of AI powered learning management system on teachers' workload. Two research questions guided this study. Descriptive correlational research design was used to investigate the impact of AI powered learning management system on students' performance and teacher workload at the National Open University Ilorin Centre. Purposive sampling technique was employed to collect data from 30 moderators who served as teachers in the faculty of education at the NOUN Ilorin study center, a structured questionnaire was employed for data collection. Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was utilized to test the hypotheses at 0.05 significance level. The findings revealed a positive correlation between AI-powered LMS and improved student performance, as well as a reduction in teacher workload. AI tools provided personalized learning experiences for students and automated several administrative tasks for educators, enhancing efficiency. Based on the findings, it is recommended that educational institutions adopt AI-powered LMS to optimize learning outcomes, reduce teacher workload, and provide continuous training to ensure effective implementation of AI tools in teaching environments.*

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, Learning Management Systems, AI-Powered Learning, Student Performance, Teacher workload

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) technology is a revolutionary technology which has recently gained ground in education globally. The effect of artificial intelligence cannot be over emphasized in all sector of the society especially in the educational sector. AI is an important aspect of many parts of human daily life; it helps us in several ways. Technology has generally been identified with improving human life, in the bid to improve learning experience AI has been integrated in the learning system. Javkhedkar et al (2024) stated that the integration of artificial intelligence in education has become increasingly popular as a result of the progress in technology globally such as artificial neural networks, deep learning, and knowledge graphs. All these developments have driven the education industry into a new age usually called Artificial Intelligence Age. AI in education can be categorized as an event that is trending, it can be found virtually in all levels of education and it has improved learning in all the levels of education (Ali et al, 2023). AI powered learning management system has been observed to be geared towards the special needs of students, customers and employees as it helps them progress.

AI powered learning management system (LMS) is an advance platform of e-learning that combines AI technologies such as data analytics, machine learning, predictive learning algorithms and many others to improve and make learning process easy and smarter. AI powered learning management systems has numerous benefits, because it has not only improved the teaching and learning processes and educational settings but has also encouraged democratic access to education by making it more flexible and accessible globally. Ali et al, (2023) explained that AI in learning management system is an indication that education has a brighter future because it offers many substantial advantages such as curriculum automation, automatic error correction and personalized content. In line with this Vergara et al (2024) also noted that the utilization of AI powered learning management systems offer personalized and adaptive learning experiences, promotes active learning, and supports self-regulated learning in face-to-face, hybrid, and online learning environments. Also, artificial intelligence learning management systems can improve students' learning motivation, engagement, performance and their tendency to increased and equal access to education by supporting open educational resources. AI-powered LMS works by providing learner with personalized recommendations, monitors students' progress and gives feedback. It also encourages team work and collaboration by using social media as a tool to connect students with their instructors and peers (Mureşan, 2023). AI powered learning management system does not only benefit learners, but it also benefits educators, and institutions because of the wider availability of mobile devices and online curriculum.

Ramakrishnan (2024) noted that AI has significant potential to improve eLearning effectiveness by leveraging on machine intelligence to perform tasks like language translation, decision-making and speech recognition. Hessah et al (2024) stated that AI-powered LMS can personalize instruction based on each student's abilities, interests and learning style and such tool also have tendency of augmenting overburdened teachers by automating routine tasks and delivering interactive content Integrated into devices, AI powered learning management system patterns offer suggestions, enhancing learning experiences. Notable examples include AI-enabled Moodle, Knewton Alta, TalentLMS, Squirrel AI Learning, and Course match. These technologies improve student engagement and performance by streamlining learning through individualized feedback and adaptive material. For example, Knewton Alta provides content according to student performance, while Moodle incorporates a number of plugins to improve its features. The systems improve learning outcomes but can also introduce difficulties, such as tutor's requirement for improved integration and digital literacy. Particularly, in the context of higher education, these technologies have proven beneficial. Seo et al (2021) also added

that AI-powered LMS have numerous benefits such as personalized learning for students and automation of teachers' routine tasks to AI-powered assessments. They further explained that AI-powered LMS can have positive effects on teaching and learning process by providing personalized guidance, support, or feedback by tailoring learning content based on student-specific learning patterns or knowledge levels. AI-powered LMS also have positive impact on teachers by helping teachers save time answering students' simple, repetitive questions in online discussion forums, and instead teachers can dedicate their saved time to higher-value work. AI-powered LMS allows teachers to understand students' performance, progress, and potential by decrypting their click-stream data. Although it's not yet standard in many learning institutions which may be due to one or all of the following challenges: Expertise and Cost, Security and Data Privacy, Integration Challenges, Organizational Resistance, Training Needs and Accountability and Transparency. In this age of technology and globalization revolution the academic performance of students is assumed to be very important for all round development of any country because students' academic performance plays important role in producing excellent human capital which will become strong manpower to saddle the growth of the company economically and socially (Duwal & Khonju, 2020).

Students' academic performance is the degree to which students have been able to achieve their short or long-term educational goals which is been measured by cumulative grade point average (CGPA) or continuous assessment (Tadese, 2022). Yousuf and Nur (2022) stated that Students' Academic Performance is imperative for evaluating a student's position academically within a university. It is the student performance that makes it possible for academic staff, educational administrators, and decision-makers to accurately assess students taking various courses all through a semester. This performance may be influenced by factors such as environmental, social, economic, psychological and personal factors. Wu et al (2024) stated that there are number of factors that determine students' academic progress and learning performance. These factors include gender, age, students' schooling, the social economic status of the students' parent or guardians, the residential area of the students, the medium of instruction in schools, the trend of tuition, the number of hours that students spend studying each day, and whether they are housed in hostels or as day scholars, teaching facilities, and method of teaching. All these factors can be categorized into student's factor, environmental factor and teacher's factor. A teacher is as important as technology is in the process of learning and teaching. Teachers play an important role in the development of any nation because they instill desired values and habits into the young one and also help them develop skills that are work oriented in the development of the society. Chukwu, et al (2026). Carried out a study on AI-Powered Learning Tools and Engagement Across Disciplines, the study examined how different AI learning tools influence student engagement and academic performance in higher education. It categorized tools by their primary focus (e.g., knowledge mastery vs. interaction frequency) and analyzed results across various disciplines, age groups, and genders. It was highlighted that tools specifically designed to support knowledge mastery were more strongly associated with academic performance than tools focused solely on interaction. The study found that while engagement patterns vary by discipline (with STEM students often showing stronger engagement), the positive impact on performance was consistent. Another research was carried out by the International Association for Computer Information Systems (2025) On the Effectiveness of AI-Driven Tools vs. Traditional Methods. The study investigated the comparative effectiveness of adaptive learning platforms and intelligent tutoring systems against traditional classroom instructional methods. It analyzed performance gains, task efficiency, and learner satisfaction. Key findings reported performance gains ranging from 15% to 35% for students using AI-supported systems. It concluded that AI's ability to provide real-time, individualized learning pathways—effectively acting as a digital tutor—significantly improves retention and mastery of complex subjects compared to "one-size-fits-all" traditional methods. The study by

Maphalala, M., & Ajani, O. A. (2025) on the Impact of AI-Driven LMS on Teaching and Learning evaluates how AI-integrated Learning Management Systems foster dynamic and flexible learning environments. It focuses on the ability of AI to address challenges like large class sizes and varying student learning paces. The findings reveal that AI-based LMS are moderately to highly effective in improving student engagement and outcomes. It highlights that while AI automates feedback, its success is dependent on robust institutional support, ethical considerations, and continuous professional development for educators to ensure they remain the center of the pedagogical process. The research carried out by Amadi, C., & Okorie, C. (2025). on "Influence of AI-Based Administrative Management Systems on Lecturers' Teaching Effectiveness." highlights how AI-driven LMS functions—such as smart feedback and automated reports assist lecturers in managing large student populations.

The study concludes that AI tools streamline repetitive instructional tasks and enhance curriculum planning, allowing lecturers to dedicate more time to innovative teaching. This shift contributes to improved academic outcomes for students by providing more responsive pedagogical approaches.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

An important function of AI-powered Learning Management Systems is to automate administrative tasks and provide real-time feedback to improve educational outcomes. Heavy workloads may be the reason some teachers are not effective in delivering their role perfectly, not that they do not have mastery of the subject they are teaching. A teacher's workload in tertiary institutions can have a major effect on their effectiveness and the academic performance of their students. Many of them deal with heavy administrative workload, increasing pressure to performance targets and large class size. This caused them to be overworked, resulting in an increased level of exhaustion and stress, subsequently affecting their effectiveness and academic performance of students. These and more are what prompted this study, the impact of AI-powered learning management system on students' performance and teachers' workload in the National Open University of Nigeria, Ilorin study center, Kwara State.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The main purpose of this study is to investigate the impact of AI powered learning management system on students' performance and teacher workload in National Open University Nigeria, Ilorin study center, Kwara State, Nigeria, while the specific purpose of the study is to:

- i. Find out the impact of AI powered learning management system on students' performance
- ii. Investigate the impact of AI powered learning management system on teachers' workload

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions were raised to guide this study:

- i. What is the impact of AI powered learning management system on students' performance?
- ii. What is the impact of AI-powered learning management system on teachers' workload?

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

The following hypotheses were formulated and were tested at 0.05 of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant impact of AI powered learning management system on students' performance

H₀₂: There is no significant impact of AI powered learning management system on teachers' workload

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research is quantitative in nature. Descriptive correlational research design was used to investigate the impact of AI powered learning management system on students' performance and teacher workload at the National Open University Ilorin Centre. Oyedeji (2023) defined correlational research design as a research design used to describe the degree of association of variables. The researcher considered this design appropriate because it described the degree of association among AI-powered learning management system, student academic performance and lecturer's workload.

Population, Sample and Sampling Technique

The population of this study comprised of all moderators in National Open University Nigeria, Ilorin study center, Kwara State, Nigeria. The moderators are referred to as lecturers in NOUN, this is because NOUN is an open and distance learning institution that uses basically digital tools to enhance learning. An open and distance learning institution is an institution where individuals are allowed to acquire needed knowledge through the use of their personal computer and access to internet, which means that an open and distance learning institutions allows learners to learn anywhere with their PC as long as it equipped with internet connection (Okop et al, 2021), for this reason both moderators and learners have higher tendency of using AI-powered LMS. While the target population is the faculty of Education moderator (teachers) of the study center, this is because they are accessible to the researcher and they are the ones that are most likely affected with heavy workload. Purposive random sampling was used to select 30 moderators, from Ilorin study center.

Instruments for Data Collection

Two instruments were used for data collection; they are raw data of Faculty of Education GNS101 result and researcher designed questionnaire. Raw data of GNS101 result for faculty of education 100 level students which measured the performance of students for a semester and was obtained from the study center with the appropriate permission. The second instrument used for data collection is a researcher designed questionnaire which contained three sections, section A-C. Section A contained the demographic characteristics of respondents while section B contained eight (8) items on AI-powered LMS, Section C contained five (5) items on teacher workload, the questionnaire was designed on 4point likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA)=4, Agree (A) =3, Disagree (D) =2 and Strongly Disagree (SD) =1.

The face and content validity were done by two test and measurement experts. The reliability of the instrument was assessed using test-retest method. The test was administered on a sample of 50 participants from another study center, who are on the list that form the population but not part of those sampled for the study. The test was re-administered after one week to confirm the internal consistency of the instrument. The results acquired were examined using the Cronbach alpha coefficient method to test the hypotheses for significance at the 0.05 level, and a reliability Coefficient of 0.84 was obtained. Signifying that the instrument is reliable.

Procedures for Data Collection

The researcher introduced herself to the coordinators at the study center. The privacy of information and other ethical assurances were guaranteed to the respondents, and the researcher administered the

instruments. Freedom to ask questions for clarification was granted, and sufficient time was given to the respondents. Each respondent answered the questions voluntarily after informed consent was obtained. The completed questionnaire was then collected for the analysis.

Methods of Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics of percentage and frequency count were used to analyse the data collected on research questions one and two, while hypothesis one and two was tested using Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (PPMC) at a 0.05 significance level through the use of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

RESULTS

Research Question 1: What is the impact of AI powered learning management system on students' performance?

Table 1: Percentage and Frequency Count of AI-Powered Learning Management system on students' performance

STATEMENTS		SA	A	D	SD	Total
AI-powered LMS gives room for students to give swift feedback that helps both teacher and learner improve the teaching and learning process	F	9	14	4	3	30
	%	30.00	46.66	13.33	10.00	100
AI-powered LMS makes learning process democratic and give access to education by making it more flexible and accessible globally	F	10	11	5	4	30
	%	33.33	36.66	16.66	13.33	100
AI powered LMS offer personalized and adaptive learning experiences, promotes active learning, and supports self-regulated learning in face-to-face, hybrid, and online learning environments	F	11	15	1	3	30
	%	36.66	50.00	3.33	10.00	100
AI powered LMS benefit educators, and institutions because of the wider availability of mobile devices and online curriculum.	F	9	12	5	4	30
	%	30.00	40.00	16.66	13.33	100
Students who actively make use of the AI-powered LMS show observable improvements in their assessment scores compared to those who do not	F	7	13	6	4	30
	%	23.33	43.33	20.00	13.33	100
The AI-powered LMS has enhanced student engagement with course materials, leading to better performance in examinations and assignments	F	8	14	4	4	30
	%	26.66	46.66	13.33	13.33	100

Students' participation in activities and discussions facilitated by the AI-powered LMS correlates with higher academic achievement in the course	F	10	10	3	7	30
	%	33.33	33.33	10.00	23.33	100
The AI-driven analytics provided by the LMS have enabled me to identify and support struggling students more effectively, resulting in improved overall class performance	F	9	13	5	3	30
	%	30.00	43.33	16.66	10.00	100

Strongly Agree (SA)= 4, Agree(A) = 3, Disagree =2, Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1

Table 1 shows that most of respondents agree that AI-powered LMS significantly enhances the teaching and learning process. Seeing from the 76.66% of respondents either strongly agreed or agreed that AI-powered LMS enables swift feedback, benefiting both teachers and students. Similarly, 70% of participants affirmed that AI-powered LMS facilitates personalized and adaptive learning experiences, which foster active learning and self-regulated learning across different teaching environments.

Moreover, the AI-powered LMS is seen as democratizing education, making learning more accessible and flexible globally, with 70% of respondents supporting this claim. The majority also acknowledged that students who use the LMS show improvements in assessment scores and engagement, as seen in statements regarding student performance and interaction with course materials. For example, 70% of the respondents agreed that the LMS has enhanced student engagement, leading to better performance in examinations and assignments. However, a small percentage disagreed, indicating some variation in student experiences with the LMS.

Research Question 2: What is the impact of AI-powered learning management system on teacher's workload?

Table 2: Percentage and Frequency Count of impact of AI-Powered Learning Management system on teacher's work load

STATEMENTS		SA	A	D	SD	Total
The AI-powered LMS has automatic routine tasks such as grading and assignment feedback, reducing the time I spend on these activities.	F	12	13	3	2	30
	%	40.00	43.33	10.00	6.66	100
Using an AI-powered LMS has allowed me to spend more time on curriculum development and student support rather than administrative tasks.	F	9	15	3	3	30
	%	30.00	50.00	10.00	10.00	100
The AI-powered LMS has simplified the process of tracking student	F	8	14	5	3	30

progress, requiring less manual effort on my part	%	26.66	46.66	16.66	10.00	100
The integration of AI-powered tools into the LMS has reduced the overall workload associated with managing large classes	F	9	13	6	2	30
	%	30.00	43.33	20.00	6.66	100
Since adopting the AI-powered LMS, I feel that my workload has become more manageable and less time-consuming	F	12	12	2	4	30
	%	40.00	40.00	6.66	13.33	100

Strongly Agree (SA)= 4, Agree(A) = 3, Disagree =2, Strongly Disagree(SD) = 1

Table 2 revealed a substantial 83.33% of respondents agreed that the LMS reduces the time spent on routine tasks like grading and providing feedback, which is reflected in teachers having more time for curriculum development and student support. The LMS also appears to streamline administrative tasks, as 73.32% of teachers felt that tracking student progress has become more manageable with less manual effort. Additionally, 83.33% of respondents felt that the integration of AI tools has reduced the workload associated with managing large classes, further highlighting the system's impact on teacher workload.

TEST OF HYPOTHESES

HYPOTHESIS ONE: There is no significant impact of AI powered learning management system on students' performance

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation of AI powered LMS and students' performance

		Students' Performance	AI powered LMS
Students' Performance	Pearson Correlation	1	.433
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.0332
	N	30	30
AI powered LMS	Pearson Correlation	.443	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.0332	
	N	30	30

Source: Survey 2024.

The first hypothesis, in table 3 posits no significant impact of AI-powered LMS on student performance, the Pearson Correlation of .433 and a significance level of .0332 suggest a moderate positive relationship between the use of AI-powered LMS and student performance. Given that the significance

value is less than 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis, concluding that AI-powered LMS has a significant positive impact on students' academic outcomes.

HYPOTHESIS TWO: There is no significant impact of AI powered learning management system on teacher's workload

Table 4: Pearson Product Moment Correlation of AI powered LMS and teacher's workload

		Teachers'Workload	AI powered LMS
Teachers 'Workload	Pearson Correlation	1	.495
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.0389
	N	30	30
AI powered LMS	Pearson Correlation	.495	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.0389	
	N	30	30

Source: Survey 2024.

The second hypothesis, in table 4 addresses the impact of AI-powered LMS on teachers' workload, the Pearson Correlation of .495 with a significance level of .0389 points to a moderate positive correlation. Since the p-value is also below 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis and accept that AI-powered LMS significantly reduces teacher workload, making their tasks more manageable and less time-consuming.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings from this study reveal significant insights into the impact of AI-powered Learning Management Systems (LMS) on student performance and teacher workload. Research Question One results show a positive correlation between the use of AI-powered LMS and student performance. Students reported enhanced engagement and motivation due to personalized learning experiences facilitated by AI technologies. This aligns with previous research suggesting that tailored educational experiences can lead to improved learning outcomes (Vergara et al., 2024). The adaptive learning capabilities of AI allow students to progress at their own pace, addressing individual learning needs and preferences. The findings further correlate with the study of Chukwu, Chukwu & Odey, 2026, Which states that Tools specifically designed to support "knowledge mastery" (such as adaptive assessments) were the strongest predictors of academic performance. The study confirmed that students who utilized these mastery-oriented tools achieved better academic outcomes compared to those using tools focused only on interaction frequency. However, it is essential to acknowledge that while AI can significantly aid learning, it cannot replace the fundamental role of effective teaching. Thus, while the LMS offers valuable resources, the integration of skilled educators remains crucial for maximizing student success.

Research Question two findings reveal that AI-powered LMS can help reduce administrative burdens on teachers, thereby enabling them to focus more on instructional activities. The automation of tasks such as grading and feedback frees up valuable time for educators, allowing them to engage more deeply with students. This aligns with previous research carried out by Iqbal, S., Khan, A., & Yasmeen, R (2026) on Quantitative Analysis on Teacher-Friendly AI Tools. The study established a positive, significant relationship between the use of AI tools and reduced teacher workload. The results

indicated that automating routine instructional and administrative processes allowed educators to focus more on student-centered pedagogy, directly correlating with improved student outcomes. However, the study also highlights a potential downside: while AI can alleviate some workload aspects, it may introduce new challenges, such as the need for ongoing training and adaptation to new technologies (Kanwal et al., 2023). Teachers may feel overwhelmed by the dual demands of integrating technology into their teaching and maintaining traditional pedagogical practices. This duality suggests a need for ongoing professional development and institutional support to effectively harness the benefits of AI.

Hypothesis one demonstrates a clear link between the use of AI features in LMS and improved student outcomes. Students who actively engaged with personalized learning paths reported higher satisfaction and achievement levels. Nonetheless, it is crucial to consider external factors that could influence academic performance, such as socioeconomic status and access to technology (Wu et al., 2024).

Hypothesis two findings partially confirm this hypothesis, as teachers indicated that AI tools helped streamline administrative tasks. However, the perception of workload reduction varied among respondents, with some educators expressing concerns about the steep learning curve associated with new technologies. This suggests that while AI has the potential to ease some pressures, effective implementation is key to realizing these benefits.

CONCLUSION

AI-powered learning management systems (LMS) improve student performance and lessen instructor workload; nevertheless, to properly integrate, continual training and assistance are needed to overcome implementation issues and optimise the educational advantages.

Most studies are of the opinion that AI-powered LMS can be used as a springboard for student success. The core findings are that by shifting from "static" learning environments to "adaptive" ones, AI helps address the different learning needs inherent in a distance-learning population like NOUN's. This personalization comes with improved engagement, higher retention rates, and better mastery of course materials.

An important opinion in recent literature is that AI-powered LMS significantly reduce the administrative burden on academic staff. For institutions with large number of students this is viewed as essential. Researchers argue that automating routine tasks such as assessments grading, managing student information and tracking attendance allows educators more free time. Although AI-powered LMS does not "replace" the teacher but rather enable them to direct their focus toward higher-level pedagogical duties.

RECOMMENDATION

The results and findings led to the formulation of the following recommendations:

1. To improve learning and teaching experiences, educational institutions must regularly offer training to instructors and students on how to use AI-powered Learning Management Systems (LMS).
2. In order to facilitate personalized learning, enhance student performance, and lessen instructor workload over time, AI-powered Learning Management Systems (LMS) need to be used as a means to modify curriculum to student needs, ultimately enabling a more efficient and effective learning environment.

3. Administrators should allocate enough resources and guarantee strong security measures for AI-powered systems in order to meet implementation problems such as cost and data privacy.
4. Schools should routinely examine the impact of AI-powered LMS on academic performance and teacher workload to optimize its deployment and increase overall efficiency.

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